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2 **RESEARCH ARTICLE**

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4 **Abscisic Acid-Triggered Persulfidation of the Cysteine Protease ATG4**
5 **Mediates Regulation of Autophagy by Sulfide**

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21 **Short title:** ATG4 is a target of sulfide

22
23 **One-sentence summary:** Hydrogen sulfide negatively regulates the progress of autophagy
24 through persulfide modification of the Arabidopsis AtATG4a protease

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29
30
31 **ABSTRACT**

32
33 Hydrogen sulfide is a signaling molecule that regulates essential processes in plants,
34 such as autophagy. In *Arabidopsis thaliana*, hydrogen sulfide negatively regulates
35 autophagy independently of reactive oxygen species via an unknown mechanism.
36 Comparative and quantitative proteomic analysis was used to detect abscisic acid-
37 triggered persulfidation that reveals a main role in the control of autophagy mediated by
38 the autophagy-related (ATG) cysteine protease AtATG4a. This protease undergoes
39 specific persulfidation of Cys170 that is a part of the characteristic catalytic Cys-His-
40 Asp triad of cysteine proteases. Regulation of the ATG4 activity by persulfidation was
41 tested in a heterologous assay using the *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* CrATG8 protein as
42 a substrate. Sulfide significantly and reversibly inactivates AtATG4a. The biological
43 significance of the reversible inhibition of the ATG4 by sulfide is supported by the
44 results obtained in Arabidopsis leaves under basal and autophagy-activating conditions.
45 A significant increase in the overall ATG4 proteolytic activity in Arabidopsis was

46 detected under nitrogen starvation and osmotic stress and can be inhibited by sulfide.
47 Therefore, the data strongly suggest that the negative regulation of autophagy by sulfide
48 is mediated by specific persulfidation of the ATG4 protease.

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50

51 **INTRODUCTION**

52

53 Hydrogen sulfide is currently recognized as a signaling molecule. In plant systems, H₂S
54 is considered to be as important as NO and H₂O₂ and regulates essential processes of
55 plant performance (Garcia-Mata and Lamattina, 2013; Calderwood and Kopriva, 2014;
56 Jin and Pei, 2015; Gotor et al., 2017). Sulfide mediates tolerance against a range of
57 plant stresses from heavy metal toxicity to salinity and drought to enhance plant
58 viability (Gotor et al., 2019). Sulfide regulates critical processes, including autophagy
59 (Alvarez et al., 2012; Gotor et al., 2013; Gotor et al., 2015; Laureano-Marin et al.,
60 2016b; Laureano-Marin et al., 2016a) and the abscisic acid (ABA)-dependent stomatal
61 movement (Jin et al., 2013; Scuffi et al., 2014; Papanatsiou et al., 2015; Scuffi et al.,
62 2018).

63 Despite increasing evidence of the biological function of H₂S, there is a considerable
64 lack of information on the mechanism of action of H₂S in particular physiological
65 processes. The mechanism of action must be related to chemical reactivity of H₂S with
66 other molecules. H₂S was suggested to coordinate the metal centers of metalloproteins
67 (Vitvitsky et al., 2018) or act as a reductant of reactive oxygen species (Zaffagnini et al.,
68 2019). A third mechanism of action of H₂S is based on its ability to modify the thiol
69 group (-SH) of the cysteine residues in target proteins to form a persulfide group (-SSH)
70 resulting in functional changes in the protein structure, activity, or subcellular
71 localizations (Aroca et al., 2015; Aroca et al., 2017b). This posttranslational
72 modification is called persulfidation (known previously as S-sulfhydration) and has
73 been initially demonstrated in the mammalian (Mustafa et al., 2009; Paul and Snyder,
74 2012) and plant systems (Aroca et al., 2015; Aroca et al., 2017a) using specific labeling
75 methods.

76 Our previous investigations in *Arabidopsis thaliana* demonstrated that hydrogen
77 sulfide functions as a signaling molecule in the cytosol that negatively regulates
78 autophagy (Alvarez et al., 2012; Gotor et al., 2013; Romero et al., 2013), which is a
79 highly conserved process involving digestion of the cell contents for recycling and

80 maintenance of cell homeostasis. Autophagy occurs at the basal levels in eukaryotic
81 cells and is induced by internal or external perturbations. In plants, autophagy is
82 involved in development, immune response, and senescence and is induced by stress
83 conditions, including nutrient limitation and other abiotic stresses (Liu and Bassham,
84 2012; Pérez-Pérez et al., 2012; Masclaux-Daubresse et al., 2017; Ustun et al., 2017;
85 Marshall and Vierstra, 2018a). This catabolic process is characterized by *de novo*
86 synthesis of autophagosomes in the cytosol, in which cytoplasmic materials to be
87 recycled are sequestered, transported, and released into the plant vacuole. Various
88 receptors have been described to assist with specific cargo recruitment and degradation
89 via selective autophagy. The core autophagy machinery is highly conserved in all
90 studied eukaryotes, and involved proteins are referred to as autophagy-related (ATG).
91 These ATG proteins include the ATG8 and ATG12 ubiquitin-like conjugation systems
92 that catalyze the covalent attachment of ATG8 to the phospholipid
93 phosphatidylethanolamine (PE), which is an essential adduct for the formation of
94 autophagosomes (Mizushima et al., 2011). Before this conjugation, the C-terminal
95 extension of newly synthesized ATG8 has to be cleaved by the Cys-type protease ATG4
96 to expose a highly conserved Gly, which is necessary for conjugation to PE.
97 Additionally, ATG4 functions as a deconjugating enzyme that cleaves the amide bond
98 between ATG8 and PE allowing the recycling of free ATG8 (Nair et al., 2012;
99 Nakatogawa et al., 2012; Yu et al., 2012).

100 The role of sulfide as a repressor of autophagy is independent of nutrient conditions
101 and specific tissues because sulfide inhibits autophagy in leaves under dark-induced
102 carbon starvation (Alvarez et al., 2012) or in roots under nitrogen deprivation
103 (Laureano-Marin et al., 2016a), and both conditions are unrelated to sulfur metabolism.
104 A study aiming to decipher the mechanism of action of H₂S showed that it is
105 independent of the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as hydrogen
106 peroxide or superoxide anions, and therefore H₂S does not serve as a reducer in the
107 regulation of autophagy (Laureano-Marin et al., 2016a). Interestingly, a comparative
108 and quantitative proteomic analysis was performed to detect endogenous persulfidated
109 proteins; the results indicated that at least 10% of the entire Arabidopsis proteome
110 undergoes persulfidation under physiological conditions suggesting a widespread
111 distribution of this posttranslational modification (Aroca et al., 2017a). Furthermore,
112 persulfidation of various components of the ABA signaling pathway has been recently

113 described as a specific mechanism of action by which H₂S controls the guard cell ABA
114 signaling (Chen et al., 2020; Shen et al., 2020).

115 In this study, a comparative and quantitative proteomic analysis was used to detect
116 persulfidated proteins in the leaves of Arabidopsis exogenously treated with ABA.
117 Interestingly, comparison of the untreated and ABA-treated samples indicated that
118 AtATG4a was the protein with the highest difference in the persulfidation level. We
119 then sought to determine whether persulfidation is the mechanism of the regulation of
120 autophagy by sulfide in Arabidopsis under the stress conditions and to ascertain whether
121 persulfidation regulates the activity of ATG4. To this aim, an enzymatic assay using
122 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* CrATG8 as ATG4 substrate was developed. In-depth
123 analysis of ATG4 proteolytic activity was performed *in vitro* and in a cell-free system
124 using total extracts from Arabidopsis under basal or autophagy-activating conditions,
125 including nitrogen limitation or osmotic stress. The results indicate that ATG4 is a
126 specific target of persulfidation.

127
128

129 **RESULTS**

130

131 **Autophagy induction by abscisic acid-triggered persulfide modification is** 132 **mediated by AtATG4a regulation by hydrogen sulfide in Arabidopsis**

133

134 Abscisic acid can trigger changes in hydrogen sulfide level and protein persulfide
135 modification in the guard cells to modulate stomatal closure (Shen et al., 2020). To
136 assess whether ABA also regulates protein persulfidation levels in the mesophyll cells, a
137 sequential window acquisition of all theoretical spectra-mass spectrometry (SWATH-
138 MS) quantitative approach was combined with the tag-switch method to measure
139 protein persulfidation (Aroca et al., 2017a). Protein samples from three biological
140 replicates (independent pools) of leaf tissue treated with ABA for 0 h (control sample),
141 3 h, and 6 h were isolated and subjected to the tag-switch procedure (Figure 1A). The
142 proteins eluted from the streptavidin beads were digested, and the peptide solutions
143 analyzed in two sequential steps: a shotgun data-dependent acquisition (DDA) approach
144 to generate the spectral library and SWATH acquisition by the data-independent
145 acquisition (DIA) method. In the first step, integration of the nine datasets resulted in
146 identification of a total of 10,329 peptides (1% FDR and 90% confidence) and 1,434

147 unique proteins (1% FDR) that were used as a spectral library (Supplemental Dataset 1).
148 In the second step, to quantify protein levels using SWATH acquisition, the same six
149 biological samples were analyzed in two technical replicates by the DIA method using
150 the LC gradient and LC-MS equipment employed in generation of the spectral library.

151 Therefore, six datasets were generated from the control and ABA-treated (for 3 and 6
152 h) samples to yield a total of 18 datasets used for the quantitative analysis. The fragment
153 spectra were extracted for the eighteen runs, and 33,887 ion transitions, 4,871 peptides,
154 and 1,157 proteins were quantified. Principal component analysis (PCA) of the protein
155 sample subgroups revealed significant reproducible data between the replicates and
156 differences between the ABA treatments (Figure 1B).

157 Comparison between the control (0 h) and the 3 h ABA treatment samples (0 h vs 3 h
158 ABA; Supplemental Dataset 2) showed that 192 proteins were more abundant in the
159 control samples with the fold change > 1.5 (p value < 0.05), and 242 proteins were less
160 abundant with the fold change < 0.66 (p value < 0.05) (Supplemental Dataset 3) (Figure
161 1C). Higher abundance of a protein in the control samples than that in the samples
162 prepared after 3 h ABA treatment means that the protein is more persulfidated in the
163 control because the tag-switch labeling recovers more protein from the streptavidin
164 column. Lower abundance in the control means that a protein is more persulfidated in
165 the 3 h ABA samples.

166 A total of 192 proteins with reduced persulfidation level after 3 h of ABA treatment
167 were analyzed based on their assigned functions and classified into 32 functional groups
168 using the MapMan nomenclature (Thimm et al., 2004; Klie and Nikoloski, 2012)
169 (Supplemental Table 1). The most numerous set corresponded to the general protein
170 group (bin 29) (Supplemental Table 2), which included 18.2% of the total identified
171 proteins with 35 total elements, 29 of which are involved in protein amino acid
172 activation (8 elements, tRNA ligases), protein synthesis (12 elements) and protein
173 degradation (9 elements). The latter group included the Cys-type protease AtATG4a
174 involved in autophagy, which showed the highest persulfidation change (5.20-fold
175 change), and the S1 RNA-BINDING RIBOSOMAL PROTEIN 1 (3.69-fold change)
176 that regulates seedling growth in the presence ABA or under abiotic stress conditions
177 (Gu et al., 2015). Additional proteins involved in the regulatory process and with a
178 reduction in their persulfidation levels included MAPK kinase 6 (MPK6, AT2G43790),
179 tyrosine phosphatase 1 (PTP1, AT1G71860), glycine-rich protein 8 (GRP8,
180 AT4G39260), and 9-cis-epoxycarotenoid dioxygenase 4 (NCED4, AT4G19170).

181 The quantitative analysis of the control and the 6 h ABA treatment samples
182 (Supplemental Dataset 4) showed a reduction in the number of regulated proteins; only
183 120 proteins were more abundant in the control *versus* the ABA treatment samples with
184 the fold change > 1.5 (p value < 0.05), and 198 proteins were less abundant with the
185 fold change < 0.66 (p value < 0.05) (Supplemental Dataset 5) (Figure 1C).

186 Comparison of differentially regulated proteins at 3 and 6 h of ABA treatment
187 showed that 42% of the proteins are regulated under both conditions and had different
188 levels of persulfidation. The cysteine protease AtATG4a showed a reduction in the level
189 of persulfidation down to only 2.45-fold after 6 h of ABA treatment compared to that
190 under the control conditions; this level was higher than that in the 3 h ABA treatment
191 samples (Figure 1D). Therefore, persulfidation level of AtATG4a was transiently
192 reduced after a short ABA treatment, and this reduction was very significant compared
193 to the untreated control.

194 The proteomics data suggest that AtATG4a protease is differentially persulfidated
195 depending on the treatment conditions; this difference may be related to the progress of
196 autophagy. To test this assumption, we analyzed the regulation of autophagy by ABA
197 treatments and the effects of sulfide under these conditions. Arabidopsis seedlings
198 expressing GFP-ATG8e fusion protein (Xiong et al., 2007) were treated with 50 μ M
199 ABA for 3 and 6 h and subjected to additional treatment of 200 μ M NaHS for 1 h. Total
200 protein extracts were obtained, and immunoblot analysis was performed using anti-GFP
201 antibodies to detect free GFP and the GFP-ATG8e fusion protein (Figure 2A). A clear
202 increase in the free GFP protein level in ABA-treated seedlings was detected compared
203 with the control and a significant reduction in the GFP accumulation after the additional
204 sulfide treatment was observed resulting in protein levels lower than those detected in
205 the control. Quantification of the ratio free GFP/GFP-ATG8 under each condition
206 showed that ABA induced the autophagic flux and that this ABA-induced autophagy
207 was repressed by NaHS (Figure 2B). These findings and the proteomic data suggest that
208 sulfide is a negative regulator of bulk autophagy independently of the condition used to
209 induce this catabolic process, including at least nutrient limitation (Alvarez et al., 2012;
210 Laureano-Marin et al., 2016a) and ABA-dependent stress (this study). Furthermore,
211 persulfidation appears to be the mechanism of action of sulfide and the AtATG4a
212 protease may be one of the specific targets.

213

214 **Persulfidation of AtATG4a at Cys170**

215

216 To demonstrate the persulfidation-based modification of Cys residues in AtATG4a,
217 recombinant protein was purified, subjected to the tag-switch procedure, and analyzed
218 by immunoblotting using anti-biotin antibodies (Aroca et al., 2017a). A biotin-labeled
219 protein band corresponding to AtATG4a was clearly detected by the antibody.
220 Moreover, when AtATG4a was pretreated with DTT to reduce the persulfide residues,
221 the biotin-labeled protein bands were not detected (Figure 3A). These results clearly
222 indicate that AtATG4a undergoes persulfidation *in vitro*. To identify the Cys residue
223 that can be modified by persulfidation, recombinant AtATG4a was analyzed by liquid
224 chromatography (LC)-tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS). The protein was digested
225 with trypsin under nonreducing conditions in the absence of alkylating agents to avoid
226 the reduction or modification of the persulfide residues. The digested peptides were
227 analyzed to detect a 32 Da molecular mass increase in the fragmentation spectrum. The
228 identified peptides included DTTYTSDVNWGCMIR that showed a persulfidation
229 modification of Cys170 (Figure 3B). AtATG4a protein was identified with a sequence
230 coverage of 97%, and no other persulfidated peptides were detected despite the presence
231 of other eleven Cys residues in the primary structure (Figure 3C). Cys170 is located in
232 the highly conserved catalytic site of ATG4 proteins from various organisms (Satoo et
233 al., 2009; Perez-Perez et al., 2014; Perez-Perez et al., 2016) suggesting that the
234 modification by persulfidation may have an important impact on the AtATG4a
235 proteolytic activity and biological function.

236

237 ***In Vitro* Processing of CrATG8 by AtATG4a**

238

239 To determine whether modification of AtATG4 by persulfidation has an effect on its
240 biological activity, an *in vitro* assay using CrATG8 from *C. reinhardtii* as a substrate
241 was established (Perez-Perez et al., 2010). CrATG8 was previously used to monitor the
242 activity of yeast ATG4 (Perez-Perez et al., 2010; Perez-Perez et al., 2014). ATG4
243 processes ATG8 at a conserved glycine residue located at the C-terminus of the protein
244 (Kirisako et al., 2000). Arabidopsis contains nine different ATG8 isoforms, none of
245 which has more than five amino acid residues after the conserved glycine (Doelling et
246 al., 2002). In contrast, CrATG8 harbors a 14-amino acid extension after the glycine, and
247 CrATG8 processing can be easily monitored by Coomassie Blue-stained SDS-PAGE

248 due to differences in mobility between the unprocessed and processed CrATG8 forms
249 (Supplemental Figure 1). When purified AtATG4a was incubated with CrATG8 in the
250 presence of DTT, the processed protein with the same mobility as a truncated form
251 lacking the last 14 amino acids (CrATG8^{G120}, referred to as pCrATG8) was detected
252 (Figure 4A). Therefore, AtATG4a was active and was able to process CrATG8 at its C-
253 terminal Gly validating the ATG4 processing activity assay. The results indicated that
254 AtATG4a activity was increased in a time-dependent manner and required a reducing
255 agent to adopt the monomeric form required for the activity (Figure 4A), as described
256 previously in other systems (Perez-Perez et al., 2010).

257 To analyze the effect of a reducing agent on AtATG4a activity, the *in vitro* assay
258 in the presence or in the absence of different DTT or TCEP concentrations was
259 performed. In the absence of DTT and TCEP, recombinant AtATG4a was in an
260 oligomeric form that was retained in the upper part of the acrylamide gel. Increasing
261 concentrations of the reducing agent enhanced the monomerization of recombinant
262 AtATG4a and consequently the processing of CrATG8 by AtATG4a (Figure 4B and
263 4C). Therefore, properties of Arabidopsis ATG4a were similar to those of the
264 Chlamydomonas and yeast ATG4 (Perez-Perez et al., 2014; Perez-Perez et al., 2016).
265 Interestingly, TCEP was more efficient than DTT in the activation of CrATG8
266 cleavage, showing the maximum level of ATG4 activity at 0.5 mM TCEP while two
267 orders of magnitude higher DTT concentration was required for optimal activity (Figure
268 4B and 4C).

269

270 **Sulfide inhibits the proteolytic activity of AtATG4a**

271

272 A suitable ATG4 enzyme activity assay was developed and used to study whether
273 persulfidation plays a role in the regulation of this activity. Thus, purified recombinant
274 AtATG4a was pretreated with TCEP to produce an active enzyme and then incubated
275 with increasing concentrations of NaHS as a sulfide donor. The ATG4 activity-
276 dependent CrATG8 processing was determined using the Coomassie-stained gel
277 method (Figure 5A). An increase in the accumulation of the unprocessed CrATG8 form
278 was detected when AtATG4a was incubated in the presence of NaHS at a concentration
279 as low as 0.1 mM. ATG4 activity was determined as the ratio of the band intensity of
280 the processed CrATG8 to the sum of the intensities of the unprocessed and processed
281 CrATG8; the data indicate that 0.1 mM NaHS significantly inhibits the ATG4 activity

282 to approximately 40% of the activity in the absence of sulfide (Figure 5B). Interestingly,
283 analysis of the aggregation state of AtATG4a in the presence of the sulfide donor
284 demonstrated that NaHS has different effects on monomerization and activity of
285 AtATG4a (Figure 5C). Sulfide did not promote the oligomerization of the active
286 monomeric AtATG4a to the same extent as it inhibited ATG4 proteolytic activity under
287 the conditions used in the assays. Concentrations of NaHS from 0.1 to 0.5 mM did not
288 significantly increase the abundance of high molecular weight and inactive oligomers of
289 AtATG4a (Figure 5C). These results indicate that sulfide donor inhibits AtATG4a
290 activity but does not directly influence the aggregation state of the protein in contrast to
291 the effect of DTT or thioredoxin on yeast and *C. reinhardtii* ATG4 proteins (Perez-
292 Perez et al., 2014; Perez-Perez et al., 2016).

293 Recent studies have questioned whether NaHS can be the sulfurating molecule
294 instead of the proposed polysulfide and persulfide molecules. These molecules contain
295 sulfane sulfur, the form of sulfur (S^0) with the ability to reversibly attach to other sulfur
296 atoms. Most of the reported biological activity associated with sulfide may be due to
297 persulfides, which are considered responsible for intracellular signal transduction
298 through persulfidation *in vivo* (Toohey, 2011; Ida et al., 2014; Mishanina et al., 2015).
299 Thus, assays similar to those described above were performed using various
300 concentrations of polysulfide Na_2S_4 used as a sulfur donor. Our results indicated that
301 polysulfide inactivates AtATG4a more efficiently than NaHS (Figure 6A and 6B).
302 Concentrations of Na_2S_4 three orders of magnitude (10-50 μ M) lower than those of
303 NaHS were necessary to achieve a similar inhibition, and complete inactivation of the
304 enzyme was observed at 100 μ M Na_2S_4 . Furthermore, polysulfides were more active in
305 promoting the aggregation of AtATG4a, and the differences in the effects on activity
306 and oligomerization were not as pronounced as those observed with NaHS (Figure 6C).

307 Collectively, our results indicate that sulfide can inhibit the ATG4 proteolytic
308 activity and that this inhibition is independent on the ATG4 aggregation state, at least at
309 low concentrations of sulfurating species. Our results also suggest that this inhibitory
310 effect is mediated by specific persulfidation of the catalytic Cys170 residue. Site-
311 directed mutagenesis of this catalytic cysteine inactivates ATG4 activity in all tested
312 systems and conditions (Scherz-Shouval et al., 2007; Shu et al., 2010; Perez-Perez et al.,
313 2014; Perez-Perez et al., 2016), and therefore the mutant enzyme cannot be used to test
314 the inhibitory effect of sulfide.

315 To examine the impact of posttranslational modification of Cys170 by persulfidation
316 on the interaction between AtATG4a and its substrate AtATG8a, 3D homology
317 modelling was performed using the structure of the *Homo sapiens* HsATG4b-LC3
318 complex (Satoo et al., 2009). AtATG4a shares up to 33.4% sequence identity with
319 HsAtg4B (E-value 7.3×10^{-90}) and AtATG8a shares up to 59.4% sequence identity with
320 HsLC3 (E-value 1.8×10^{-40}) with conserved residues covering the whole sequence.
321 Persulfidation of Cys170 in the AtATG4a-AtATG8a protein complex caused
322 conformational changes and intramolecular rearrangements of the catalytic site (Figure
323 7A) influencing substrate recognition. Addition of the –SH group to Cys170 induced an
324 unfavorable steric effect particularly affecting the His366 residue since the imidazole
325 C δ 2 and N ϵ 2 atoms are 2.9 Å and 3.4 Å from the S atom of Cys170, respectively. The
326 additional sulfur and hydrogen atoms have a covalent radius of 1.02 Å and 0.37 Å,
327 respectively (Figure 7B). Therefore, this cysteine modification can inhibit the activity of
328 the plant AtATG4a protein.

329 Interestingly, the simulation of surface electrostatic potential reveals the differences
330 between HsATG4b-LC3 and AtATG4a-AtATG8a protein complexes; specifically, the
331 electrostatic potential surface around the catalytic site of the human complex is more
332 electronegative compared to that of the Arabidopsis complex (Supplemental Figure 2).
333 However, cysteine persulfidation does not perturb the charge, since the additional –SH
334 group is a neutral contribution. A closer look at the catalytic cavity region suggests that
335 it is somewhat smaller and less exposed to the solvent in Arabidopsis compared to the
336 human homologue likely hampering the accessibility of the substrate. Overall, these
337 data suggest that inhibition of the processing activity of Arabidopsis AtATG4a may be
338 due to a conformational change of the catalytic site induced by persulfidation.

339

340 **Endogenous Arabidopsis ATG4 processes CrATG8 for conjugation**

341

342 Our results indicate that sulfide can regulate ATG4 proteolytic activity through
343 persulfidation of a specific cysteine residue. This conclusion is based on *in vitro*
344 experiments. If sulfide has a biological role in the control of ATG4 activity in living
345 plants, the inhibitory effect of sulfide should be reversible. To explore this hypothesis,
346 active AtATG4a was inhibited by a high concentration of Na₂S₄ to promote complete
347 inactivation and to determine the extent of reversion by reduction of all persulfide
348 residues with TCEP. The reactivation of AtATG4a was monitored as the ratio of the

349 protein band intensities of unprocessed and processed CrATG8 (Figure 6D). The results
350 clearly confirm that the inhibition of ATG4 proteolytic activity by sulfide is reversible,
351 suggesting that it may play a role in the control of ATG4 *in vivo*.

352 To determine whether sulfide regulation of ATG4 also occurs *in vivo*, ATG4 enzyme
353 activity was detected in Arabidopsis leaves using the addition of exogenous CrATG8 to
354 leaf protein extracts. Immunoblot analysis using antibodies against CrATG8 indicated
355 that CrATG8 was efficiently processed by incubation with Arabidopsis leaf protein
356 extracts (Figure 8A, right part). To confirm the specificity of the CrATG8 cleavage
357 assay, Arabidopsis leaf protein extracts were incubated with a mutant of CrATG8 with
358 conserved Gly-120 replaced by Ala (G120A). This CrATG8 mutant is not processed by
359 ATG4 (Perez-Perez et al., 2010; Perez-Perez et al., 2016). When G120A was used as
360 the substrate, the processed form was not detected, demonstrating the specificity of the
361 endogenous ATG4 activity in Arabidopsis (Figure 8A, left part). Moreover, in addition
362 to full-length and processed CrATG8, the antibodies specifically recognized other bands
363 with faster mobility than pCrATG8 (Figure 8, asterisks). These bands were exclusively
364 detected when wild type CrATG8, but not the G120A mutant, was used in the assay and
365 they apparently correspond to the conjugated form of CrATG8 protein, as demonstrated
366 previously in *Chlamydomonas* (Perez-Perez et al., 2010). Incubation of the Arabidopsis
367 protein extract with the processed form of the CrATG8 (pCrATG8), which does not
368 require cleavage by ATG4 and can be conjugated to PE (Supplemental Figure 3),
369 confirmed that the faster mobility bands correspond to lipidated forms. The antibodies
370 detected mainly an intense protein band that was progressively accumulated with
371 incubation time and fully lipidated at the shortest time of incubation with the extracts
372 under autophagy-activating conditions induced by nitrogen deficiency (Supplemental
373 Figure 3). Therefore, our data demonstrated that the Arabidopsis protein extracts
374 contain all the active proteins required for the conjugation of ATG8 and efficiently
375 recognize CrATG8, thus validating the results of the ATG4 activity assay in the cell-
376 free total extract.

377 To confirm the conclusion that Arabidopsis ATG4 proteins catalyze the processing
378 of CrATG8 in the cell-free total extract assay, the ATG4 enzyme activity of the
379 Arabidopsis protein extracts prepared from the *atg4ab* double-mutant seedlings was
380 assayed (Supplemental Figure 4) (Yoshimoto et al., 2004; Chung et al., 2010). When
381 CrATG8 was incubated with the Arabidopsis *atg4ab* protein extract, the processed form
382 of CrATG8 was not detected even after extended incubation. Similarly, when protein

383 extracts were prepared from nitrogen-limited seedlings, the immunoblot analysis
384 revealed a prominent protein band corresponding to the lipidated form of CrATG8 only
385 in the presence of protein extracts from wild-type plants but not from the *atg4ab* mutant
386 (Figure 8B).

387 Therefore, our data show that endogenous Arabidopsis ATG4 proteins recognize the
388 cleavage site of the Chlamydomonas ATG8 substrate, which is efficiently processed in
389 the cell-free enzymatic assay.

390

391 **Sulfide reversibly inhibits the ATG4 activity in Arabidopsis seedlings**

392

393 The effect of a sulfurating species on endogenous Arabidopsis ATG4 proteins was
394 investigated to confirm the results obtained in *in vitro* analysis. Leaf protein extracts
395 were treated with polysulfide, and CrATG8-processing activity was compared with that
396 in the untreated extract. A pronounced decrease in the ATG4 activity was observed
397 when the Arabidopsis extract was pretreated with Na₂S₄ (Figure 9A). Additionally,
398 treatment of the Arabidopsis leaf protein extract with the alkylating agent
399 iodoacetamide inhibited ATG4 activity as expected because ATG4 is a Cys protease
400 and its activity is dependent on the catalytic Cys; this effect was similar to the effect of
401 polysulfide (Figure 9A, left panel). Thus, these findings strongly suggest that sulfide
402 negatively regulates ATG4 activity *in vivo*, at least the cleavage activity of the C-
403 terminal extension of ATG8. Reversibility of the inhibitory effect of polysulfide was
404 also analyzed. When the polysulfide-incubated Arabidopsis extract was treated with
405 TCEP as a reducing agent to reduce the persulfide-modified cysteine residues in the
406 protein extract, a significant difference in the activity was detected compared with that
407 in the polysulfide-treated extract (Figure 9A, right panel). When the extract was
408 incubated with Na₂S₄, the processed CrATG8 form was barely detected; however,
409 incubation with TCEP significantly increased the abundance of this band, suggesting
410 that sulfide may inhibit Arabidopsis ATG4 activity in a reversible manner.

411 To characterize the inhibition of ATG4 proteolytic activity by sulfide, the effect of
412 polysulfide on the ATG4 activity was assayed under basal and autophagy-inducing
413 conditions. Two different established conditions of autophagy induction were tested:
414 nitrogen deficiency, which has been extensively characterized previously (Doelling et
415 al., 2002; Hanaoka et al., 2002; Xiong et al., 2005; Phillips et al., 2008; Guiboileau et
416 al., 2013; Laureano-Marin et al., 2016aa), and osmotic stress (Liu et al., 2009) imposed

417 by the addition of mannitol to the growth medium, which induces ABA-dependent
418 signaling pathway. The processed form of CrATG8 was detected in total extracts under
419 the control and autophagy-activating conditions, and sulfide inhibited endogenous
420 ATG4 activity under both conditions (Figure 9B). The faster-mobility protein band
421 corresponding to the lipidated form of CrATG8 was more prominent under nitrogen
422 limitation than osmotic stress; however, sulfide treatment decreased the accumulation of
423 the conjugated forms of CrATG8 under both conditions.

424

425

426 **DISCUSSION**

427

428 Accumulating evidence emphasizes the importance of autophagy in plant growth and
429 development. This catabolic process is highly dynamic and occurs at the basal levels to
430 maintain cellular homeostasis during growth; however, autophagy is fine-tuned to
431 adjust plant metabolism to internal and external perturbations. Various regulators of
432 autophagy have been identified in plant systems, such as the energy sensor Snf1-related
433 protein kinase 1 (SnRK1), the kinase Target of Rapamycin (TOR), the TOR
434 downstream substrate ATG1 kinase complex, and the ER stress sensor inositol-
435 requiring enzyme-1 (IRE1) (Marshall and Vierstra, 2018b; Soto-Burgos et al., 2018).

436 Other regulators of autophagy, such as hydrogen sulfide, have been identified
437 although the details of the molecular mechanism of action of these regulators remain
438 poorly understood. In the animal systems, interactions of sulfide with autophagy have
439 been described in various pathologies; depending on the disease, sulfide can either
440 suppress or activate autophagy. In all cases, hydrogen sulfide has protective effects
441 (Sen, 2017; Wang et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2018). Despite substantial progress, the exact
442 mechanism of autophagy regulation by sulfide in mammals remains unknown. In plants,
443 particularly in *Arabidopsis*, the interplay between sulfide and autophagy has been
444 shown, and progress in understanding of the mechanism has been obtained. Hydrogen
445 sulfide generated in the cytosol functions as a signaling molecule negatively regulating
446 autophagy independently of the nutritional conditions. Furthermore, sulfide was shown
447 to repress autophagy via a mechanism that is independent of redox conditions (Alvarez
448 et al., 2012; Laureano-Marin et al., 2016a).

449 Sulfur and autophagy are also linked by the mechanism of *Arabidopsis* sensing of the
450 sulfur-containing amino acid cysteine. Two different pathways have been identified for

451 sensing of its carbon/nitrogen precursor and its sulfur precursor. The sulfur precursor is
452 transduced to TOR by downregulation of glucose metabolism; therefore, sulfide
453 increases glucose levels and TOR kinase activity, downregulating autophagy (Dong et
454 al., 2017). This study demonstrated that cytosolic sulfide is not the signal responsible
455 for the regulation but does not exclude chloroplast sulfide as the signaling molecule. In
456 fact, a proteomic study showed that other sulfurating species in addition to the cytosolic
457 sulfide can be responsible for regulation of diverse biological processes (Aroca et al.,
458 2017a).

459 The data of the present study emphasize sulfide regulation of autophagy. Our
460 findings indicate that ABA activates autophagy and hydrogen sulfide downregulates
461 this catabolic process. A link between autophagy and ABA was previously described
462 through the Arabidopsis multistress regulator TSPO, a tryptophan-rich sensory protein-
463 related. ABA induces TSPO as a heme scavenger, which binds the excessive or
464 deleterious heme and then is targeted for degradation through autophagy (Vanhee and
465 Batoko, 2011; Vanhee et al., 2011). Other connections between autophagy and ABA
466 signaling via TOR have been described. Under nonstressed conditions, TOR
467 phosphorylation of ABA receptors leads to inactivation of SnRK2 kinases and disrupts
468 ABA signaling. Under abiotic stress conditions, ABA activates SnRK2 that
469 phosphorylates RAPTOR resulting in the inhibition of TOR and consequential
470 activation of autophagy (Wang et al., 2018).

471 Previous studies have shown that the main mechanism of action of sulfide involves
472 persulfidation of reactive cysteine residues of the target proteins resulting in changes in
473 enzyme structure, activity and subcellular localization previously demonstrated in
474 several target plant proteins (Aroca et al., 2015; Aroca et al., 2017b; Aroca et al., 2018).
475 A proteomic analysis performed on mature leaves from Arabidopsis plants grown under
476 nonstress conditions revealed that a high proportion of the whole Arabidopsis proteome
477 may undergo persulfidation under the basal conditions (Aroca et al., 2017a). In this
478 study, a comparative and quantitative proteomic analysis has been performed on ABA-
479 treated leaves to determine whether persulfidation mechanism is involved in sulfide
480 regulation of the ABA signaling pathways. Significant differences in the levels of
481 persulfidation were observed after ABA treatment compared to that under the control
482 conditions. Surprisingly, the protein with the lowest level of persulfidation after 3 h
483 ABA treatment was identified as Cys-type protease AtATG4a (5.20-fold change,
484 $p < 0.05$, control *versus* 3h ABA), and even after 6 h of ABA treatment, the reduction in

485 the level of persulfidation remained very significant (2.46-fold change, $p < 0.05$, control
486 *versus* 6 h ABA). These data suggest that AtATG4a may be a target of persulfidation
487 and that this posttranslational modification may be the molecular mechanism mediating
488 sulfide regulation of autophagy. A detailed analysis of the ABA-triggered changes in
489 the persulfidation proteome will be performed in a future study. Our results
490 demonstrated that ATG4 proteolytic activity in Arabidopsis is reversibly regulated by
491 sulfide, and this regulation effectively controls the progression of autophagy. Thus, our
492 findings contribute to the understanding of the mechanism of regulation of autophagy
493 by sulfide in the plant systems and add another level of regulation to this process.

494 The AtATG4a protease contains a specific site of persulfidation detected by the tag-
495 switch procedure and confirmed by mass spectrometry. The specifically persulfidated
496 cysteine residue is Cys170, which is a part of the characteristic catalytic triad Cys-His-
497 Asp of cysteine proteases (Sugawara et al., 2005). Comparison of the amino acid
498 sequences of ATG4s from various biological systems indicated low similarity although
499 the amino acids required for the cysteine protease activity, including the catalytic
500 Cys170, are highly conserved. Interestingly, Cys170 is the only Cys residue that is
501 conserved in all known ATG4s (Supplemental Figure 5) (Perez-Perez et al., 2014;
502 Perez-Perez et al., 2016; Seo et al., 2016). In contrast, redox regulation of specific Cys
503 residues has been detected in ATG4 from human, yeast, and *Chlamydomonas*.
504 However, these residues are not conserved in various organisms and therefore the
505 details of the regulatory mechanisms may be different. In humans, HsATG4a and
506 HsATG4b proteases are the targets of reversible oxidation by H_2O_2 , and the cysteine
507 residue Cys81 located close to the catalytic Cys residue (Cys77, analogous to Cys170 in
508 Arabidopsis) was shown to be critical for this regulation (Scherz-Shouval et al., 2007).
509 Recently, Cys292 and Cys361 have been shown to be HsATG4b sites essential for
510 reversible oxidative modification (Zheng et al., 2020). Redox regulation of the yeast
511 ScATG4 protein is due to the formation of a disulfide bond between the noncatalytic
512 residues Cys338 and Cys394, which is thioredoxin-dependent (Perez-Perez et al., 2014).
513 In *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*, CrATG4 activity depends on the formation of a single
514 disulfide bond regulated by the NADPH/thioredoxin system; however, only Cys400,
515 which is the equivalent to Cys338 in yeast, has been demonstrated to be required for
516 redox regulation of the algal CrATG4 enzyme (Perez-Perez et al., 2016). In
517 Arabidopsis, the activity of AtATG4a and AtATG4b is reversibly inhibited *in vitro* by
518 reactive oxygen species (Woo et al., 2014), although redox regulation of the critical

519 cysteine residues was not reported. Additionally, other posttranslational modifications
520 of cysteine residues of ATG4 proteases have been described, such as S-nitrosylation of
521 HsATG4b at Cys189 and Cys292, though these two residues are not conserved in the
522 HsATG4a amino acid sequence (Li et al., 2017). Therefore, persulfidation of the
523 catalytic Cys residue of cysteine proteases ATG4 can be a posttranslational
524 modification conserved in various biological systems.

525 Because the target residue of persulfidation involves the active site, an effect of the
526 sulfide donor molecules on the enzymatic activity of AtATG4a was anticipated. In fact,
527 a 3D modelling analysis predicted that the addition of a sulfur atom to the -SH group of
528 Cys170 can cause unfavorable effects on the catalytic site of AtATG4a that should
529 affect substrate recognition and impair the enzyme activity. To test this hypothesis, a
530 heterologous activity assay was developed using CrATG8 as a substrate similar to
531 previously reported assays (Perez-Perez et al., 2014; Seo et al., 2016). Our results
532 indicate that the plant protease is functional and can process the algal substrate.

533 Our findings demonstrate that sulfide plays a specific role in the regulation of ATG4
534 enzymatic activity. The sulfide donor molecules used in this study, such as hydrosulfide
535 and tetrasulfide, significantly inactivate AtATG4a cleavage activity even at relatively
536 low concentrations, being polysulfide the most efficient inhibitor. The chemical
537 mechanism of the reaction of the thiol groups with the sulfide molecule remains a
538 matter of debate. H₂S cannot directly react directly with thiols, and the cysteine group
539 must be partially oxidized (converted to disulfide, glutathiolated, S-nitrosylated, or to
540 sulfenic acid) prior to sulfide attack. Alternatively, certain chemical studies have
541 demonstrated that sulfane sulfur (S⁰) of the polysulfide molecule is responsible for the
542 production of persulfide during interaction with the thiol group (Toohey, 2011; Kimura,
543 2015; Mishanina et al., 2015). This phenomenon can explain why polysulfide is a more
544 potent inhibitor of ATG4 activity than hydrosulfide. Moreover, the inhibitory effect of
545 low concentrations of sulfide on AtATG4a activity compatible with the *in vivo*
546 conditions is reversible by a reducing agent suggesting a biological role of this effect.
547 Interestingly, an enzymatic mechanism of reversing persulfidation by the thioredoxin
548 system has been demonstrated in animal systems (Wedmann et al., 2016; Doka et al.,
549 2020). Thus, it is plausible that the thioredoxin system also functions in plants to
550 modulate the activity of AtATG4.

551 The biological significance of sulfide regulation of autophagy through reversible
552 inhibition of ATG4 protease is reinforced by the assays in Arabidopsis leaves under

553 basal and autophagy-inducing conditions. Our experimental system was shown to be
554 suitable for specific assay of Arabidopsis ATG4 processing activity by using various
555 experimental approaches. Endogenous plant ATG4 cysteine proteases specifically
556 recognize the Gly120 cleavage site in the substrate from green algae based on the
557 experiment with the G120A mutant of the CrATG8 substrate. The processed form was
558 not detected when the Arabidopsis protein extracts were deficient in ATG4a and
559 ATG4b enzymes, demonstrating the specificity of our experimental system. The
560 endogenous Arabidopsis ATG4 proteins mimic the effect of sulfurating molecules on
561 AtATG4a *in vitro*, including significant inhibition by the sulfide donor and reversal by a
562 reducing agent. A significant increase in the overall ATG4 protease activity in
563 Arabidopsis was detected under autophagy-inducing conditions, including nitrogen
564 starvation and osmotic stress. Thus, a correlation was detected between the progress of
565 autophagy and the ATG4 enzymatic activity estimated using the heterologous assay
566 method. Additionally, the inhibitory effect of sulfide on the protease activity was
567 observed under the conditions of induced autophagy. Overall, our findings suggest that
568 negative regulation of the progress of autophagy by sulfide is mediated by specific
569 persulfidation of cysteine protease ATG4. However, additional targets of sulfide cannot
570 be ruled out and further analysis is needed.

571 In conclusion, our data suggest a new level of regulation of ATG4 activity by sulfide.
572 Based on our findings, we propose that intracellular sulfide maintains high levels of
573 persulfidation of the ATG4 pool under basal conditions, resulting in the inhibition of
574 ATG4 proteolytic activity. ATG4 inhibition limits the formation of ATG8-PE adducts
575 and consequently *de novo* synthesis of autophagosomes. An increase in the intracellular
576 level of ABA transiently reduces the level of persulfidation of the ATG4 population and
577 then activates the protease activity of the enzyme to process ATG8 that can be further
578 lipidated (Figure 10).

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582

581 **METHODS**

583 **Plant Material, Treatments and Protein Extraction**

584 Plant growth conditions were 16 h of light ($120 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) at 22°C and 8 h of dark at
585 20°C. The *Arabidopsis thaliana* wild-type and the *atg4ab* mutant (Nottingham
586 Arabidopsis Stock Center) seeds were sown on Murashige and Skoog (MS) solid
587 medium containing 0.8% (w/v) agar, synchronized at 4°C for 2 d, and incubated

588 vertically in a growth chamber (LUMILUX Cool White bulbs). For exposure to the
589 nitrogen-starvation conditions, nitrogen-deficient MS medium was prepared by
590 replacing nitrate salts with chloride salts. For mannitol treatment, 300 mM was added to
591 the MS medium. One-week-old seedlings were transferred to nitrogen-deficient or
592 mannitol-containing MS solid medium for an additional 4 d of growth.

593 For proteomic analysis, wild-type *Arabidopsis* plants were grown in soil for 30 days,
594 and then sprayed with water (control conditions), or 50 μ M ABA for 3 and 6 h. To
595 assess the autophagic activity, one-week-old *Arabidopsis* seedlings overexpressing
596 GFP-ATG8e (Xiong et al., 2007) were transferred to the MS liquid medium and treated
597 with 50 μ M ABA for 3 and 6 h and with 200 μ M NaHS for 1 h.

598 *Arabidopsis* material (200 mg) was ground in liquid nitrogen with 400 mL of
599 extraction buffer (100 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 400 mM sucrose, 1 mM EDTA, 0.1 mM
600 phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF)) using a mortar and pestle. After centrifugation
601 at 500 g for 10 min at 4°C, the supernatant was used as the *Arabidopsis* protein extract.

602

603 **Persulfidated Protein Quantitation by Label-free SWATH-MS Acquisition and** 604 **Analysis**

605 Protein samples from three biological replicates (independent pools) of leaf tissues
606 treated with ABA for 0 h (control sample), 3 h and 6 h were isolated and 1 mg of
607 protein per sample was used for the tag-switch labeling for enrichment of persulfidated
608 proteins as described (Aroca et al, 2017). After elution from the streptavidin beads, the
609 proteins were precipitated by TCA/acetone. Precipitated samples were resuspended in
610 50 mM ammonium bicarbonate with 0.2% Rapigest (Waters) for protein determination.
611 Protein (50 μ g) was digested with trypsin as described previously (García et al., 2019;
612 Vowinckel et al., 2014), and the SWATH-MS analysis was performed at the Proteomic
613 Facility of the Institute of Plant Biochemistry and Photosynthesis, Seville, Spain. A
614 data-dependent acquisition (DDA) approach using nano-LC-MS/MS was initially
615 performed to generate the SWATH-MS spectral library as described by García et al.,
616 (2019).

617 The peptide and protein identifications were performed using Protein Pilot software
618 (version 5.0.1, Sciex) with the Paragon algorithm. The search was conducted against a
619 Uniprot proteome (June 2017, release), and the corresponding reversed entries and
620 common contaminants were assembled in the FASTA format using ProteinPilot

621 software v5.0.1 (AB Sciex) with the Paragon algorithm. Samples were input as
622 unlabeled with no special factors, trypsin digested and MSBT alkylated. The
623 automatically generated report in ProteinPilot was manually inspected for FDR (false
624 discovery rate) cut-off proteins and only proteins identified at $FDR \leq 1\%$ were
625 considered for output and subsequent analysis.

626 For relative quantification using SWATH analysis, the same samples used to
627 generate the spectral library were analyzed using a data-independent acquisition (DIA)
628 method. Each sample (2 μ L) was analyzed using SWATH-MS acquisition method on
629 the LC-MS equipment with the LC gradient as described. The method consisted of
630 repeated acquisition cycles of TOF MS/MS scans (230 to 1500 m/z, 60 ms acquisition
631 time) of 60 overlapping sequential precursor isolation windows of variable width (1 m/z
632 overlap) covering the 400-1250 m/z mass range from a previous TOF MS scan (400-
633 1250 m/z, 50 ms acquisition time) for each cycle. The total cycle time was 3.7 s.

634 Autocalibration of the equipment and chromatographic conditions were controlled by
635 an injection of a standard of digested β -galactosidase from *E coli* between the replicates.

636 SWATH MS spectra alignment was performed with the PeakView 2.2 (Sciex)
637 software with the MicroApp SWATH 2.0 using the reference spectral library generated
638 as described above. Two DIA raw files for each biological replicate were loaded in
639 unison using the following parameters: 10 peptides, 7 transitions, peptide confidence
640 $>99\%$, 1% FDR including shared peptides, and XIC width set at 0.05 Da. After data
641 processing, three distinct files were exported for subsequent quantification. The
642 processed mrkvw files containing protein information from PeakView were loaded into
643 MarkerView (Version 1.2.1, AB Sciex) for normalization of protein intensity (peak
644 area) for all runs using the built-in total ion intensity sum plug-in. \log_2 transformation
645 was performed prior to statistical analysis. A histogram plot was used to check the
646 normality of distribution of each technical replicate. Mean values of protein expression
647 were used for calculation of fold change (FC). Proteins with adjusted $p < 0.05$ and
648 $FC \geq 1.5$ were considered differentially expressed.

649 The mass spectrometry proteomic data have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange
650 Consortium via the PRIDE (Vizcaino et al, 2016) partner repository with the identifier
651 PXD019802.

652

653 **Expression of AtATG4a in *Escherichia coli***

654 Total RNA was extracted from wild-type Arabidopsis leaves using an RNeasy plant
655 mini kit (Qiagen) and reverse-transcribed using an oligo (dT) primer and a SuperScript
656 first-strand synthesis system for RT-PCR (Invitrogen). Subsequently, a 1,404 bp
657 sequence encoding the full-length AtATG4a (At2g44140) protein was amplified by
658 PCR using the primers ATG4-F: CACCATGAAGGCTTTATGTGA and ATG4-R:
659 ATGACTGGCAAATGCTCTGA and the proofreading Platinum Pfx DNA polymerase
660 (Invitrogen). The PCR conditions were as follows: a denaturation cycle of 2 min at 94°C
661 followed by 30 amplification cycles of 15 s at 94°C, 30 s at 57°C, and 1 min at 68°C.
662 The amplified cDNA was then ligated into the pENTR/D-TOPO vector using the
663 pENTR directional TOPO cloning kit (Invitrogen) according to the manufacturer's
664 instructions. Positive clones were identified by PCR and selected for plasmid DNA
665 isolation. The *AtATG4a* cDNA was then cloned into the expression vector pDEST17
666 using an *E. coli* expression system with gateway technology (Invitrogen), which
667 generates a fusion protein with an N-terminal 6x His tag that was confirmed by
668 sequencing; the expression was induced with L-arabinose in BL21-AI *E. coli* cells.

669

670 **Purification of the Recombinant AtATG4a Protein**

671 The 6x His-tagged recombinant protein was isolated from 200 mL of BL21-AI *E. coli*
672 cells that were cultured at 37°C to an optical density of 0.5 at 600 nm and induced with
673 0.2% (w/v) L-arabinose for 2.5 h at 37°C. Prior to purification, His-tagged AtATG4a
674 was solubilized with 6 M urea because the recombinant protein was contained in the
675 inclusion bodies. Then, the protein was purified from the soluble fraction by nickel
676 affinity chromatography using an Invitrogen Ni-NTA Purification System
677 (ThermoFisher Scientific), according to the manufacturer's instructions. The purified
678 protein was concentrated and desalted using 10 kD cutoff pore size centrifugal filter
679 units (Millipore). The purity of the protein was confirmed by SDS-PAGE using 12%
680 (w/v) polyacrylamide gels stained by Coomassie Blue.

681

682 **Detection of Persulfidation on the Recombinant AtATG4a**

683 An untreated aliquot of the purified recombinant AtATG4a and another aliquot
684 pretreated with 50 mM DTT for 30 min at 4°C to reduce all persulfide groups were
685 precipitated with acetone for 20 min at -20°C and centrifuged at a maximum speed for
686 20 min at 4°C. After acetone removal, the proteins were resuspended in 50 mM Tris-
687 HCl (pH 8) buffer supplemented with 2.5% (w/v) SDS and subjected to the tag-switch

688 procedure as described previously (Aroca et al., 2017a). The CN-biotinylated proteins
689 were then detected using an immunoblot assay as follows. The CN-biotinylated proteins
690 were separated using nonreducing SDS-PAGE through 12% (w/v) polyacrylamide gels
691 and transferred to polyvinylidene difluoride membranes (Bio-Rad) according to the
692 manufacturer's instructions. The anti-biotin (Abcam, catalog # ab191354) and
693 secondary antibodies (Bio-Rad, catalog # 170-6515) were diluted 1:500,000 and
694 1:100,000, respectively, and ECL Select western blotting detection reaction (GE
695 Healthcare) was used to detect the proteins using horseradish peroxidase-conjugated
696 anti-rabbit secondary antibodies. For protein loading control, the membranes before
697 immunodetection were stained with SYPRO Ruby (Invitrogen) to detect all protein
698 bands.

699

700 **Identification of Persulfidated Cys Residues of Recombinant AtATG4a Using** 701 **Mass Spectrometry**

702 Recombinant AtATG4a was separated using nonreducing SDS-PAGE through 12%
703 (w/v) polyacrylamide gels, and the band corresponding to AtATG4a was manually
704 excised from Coomassie-stained gels. Gel plugs were washed twice using 50 mM
705 ammonium bicarbonate and acetonitrile and dried under a stream of nitrogen. Then,
706 proteomics-grade trypsin (Sigma-Aldrich) at a final concentration of 16 ng/ μ l in 25%
707 (v/v) acetonitrile/50 mM ammonium bicarbonate solution was added; the samples were
708 digested at 37°C for 5 h. The reaction was stopped by adding 50% (v/v)
709 acetonitrile/0.5% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid for peptide extraction. The eluted tryptic
710 peptides were dried by speed-vacuum centrifugation and resuspended in 6 μ l of 0.1%
711 (v/v) formic acid in water. Digested peptides were subjected to nanoliquid
712 chromatography electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry analysis using a
713 nanoliquid chromatography system (ExcionLC AD, Sciex) coupled to a TripleTOF
714 5600+ mass spectrometer (Sciex) with a spray ionization source. Mass spectrometry and
715 MS/MS data of individual samples were processed using the Analyst TF 1.5.1 software
716 (Sciex). Peptide mass tolerance was set to 25 μ D D^{-1} and 0.05 D for fragment masses,
717 and only one or two missed cleavages were allowed. Peptides with an individual M_r
718 search score ≥ 20 were considered correctly identified.

719

720 ***In vitro* ATG4 Enzyme Activity Assay**

721 The typical reaction mixture contained 5 μ M recombinant AtATG4a, 5 μ M CrATG8
722 (Perez-Perez et al., 2010), and 1 mM EDTA in Tris-buffered saline (50 mM Trizma
723 base, 138 mM NaCl, and 27 mM KCl at pH 8). When indicated, AtATG4a was
724 incubated in the presence of DTT, TCEP, NaHS, Na₂S₄, or iodoacetamide alone or in
725 combination at the indicated times and concentrations. The reaction mixtures were
726 incubated at 25°C, and the reaction was stopped by the addition of β -mercaptoethanol-
727 free Laemmli sample buffer followed by 5 min boiling. The proteins were resolved
728 using nonreducing SDS-PAGE through 15% (w/v) polyacrylamide gels and stained
729 with Coomassie Brilliant Blue (Sigma-Aldrich). The gels were scanned with a GS-800
730 densitometer (Bio-Rad), and the signals corresponding to the unprocessed and
731 processed CrATG8 forms were quantified with the Quantity One software (Bio-Rad).
732 The ATG4 activity (in arbitrary units) was calculated as the ratio of the band intensity
733 of the processed CrATG8 to the sum of the intensities of the unprocessed and processed
734 CrATG8. An activity value of 1 corresponds to the maximum value.

735

736 **Assay of Endogenous ATG4 Enzyme Activity in Cell-Free Total Extract**

737 The *in vivo* assay of ATG4 activity in cell-free total extract was performed in a typical
738 reaction mixture containing 40 μ g of leaf or 20 μ g of root protein extract and 0.05 μ M
739 purified unprocessed CrATG8, processed pCrATG8, or Gly-to-Ala mutant protein
740 (G120A). When required, a sulfur donor (Na₂S₄), a reducing agent (TCEP), or an
741 alkylating agent (IAM) was added at the indicated concentrations. The reaction mixture
742 was incubated at 25°C for the indicated time, stopped by addition of β -mercaptoethanol-
743 free Laemmli sample buffer, and boiled for 5 min. Then, proteins were separated using
744 nonreducing SDS-PAGE through 15% (w/v) polyacrylamide gels and transferred to
745 nitrocellulose membranes (Bio-Rad) as described previously (Perez-Perez et al., 2010).
746 Anti-CrATG8 (Pérez-Pérez et al., 2010) and secondary antibodies were diluted 1:3,000
747 and 1:10,000, respectively. An ECL Select western blotting detection reaction (GE
748 Healthcare) was used to detect the proteins. For protein loading control, the membranes
749 before immunodetection were stained with Ponceau S (Sigma-Aldrich) to detect all
750 protein bands.

751

752 **Protein modeling**

753 3D homology modeling was driven by Modeller (Sali and Blundell, 1993) using the
754 structure of the *Homo sapiens* Atg4B-LC3 complex (PDB ID: 2Z0E) (Sato et al., 2009)
755 as a template. Molecular crystal X-ray structures and structural model of *Arabidopsis*
756 *thaliana* AtATG4a-AtATG8a complex were inspected, analyzed and plotted with
757 PyMol 1.4.1 (Schrodinger LLC). Surface electrostatic potentials were calculated and
758 visualized using the PyMol 1.4.1 software.

759

760 **Accession Numbers**

761 The mass spectrometry proteomic data have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange
762 Consortium via the PRIDE partner repository with the identifier PXD019802. Sequence
763 data from this article can be found in the EMBL/GenBank data libraries under the
764 following accession numbers: *AtATG4a* (At2g44140), *AtATG4b* (At3g59950), *AtATG8a*
765 (At4g21980) and *CrATG8* (Cre16.g689650.t1.1).

766

767

768 **SUPPLEMENTAL DATA**

769 **Supplemental Figure 1.** C-Termini of the Chlamydomonas ATG8 proteins and nine
770 Arabidopsis ATG8 proteins.

771 **Supplemental Figure 2.** Simulation of surface electrostatic potential distribution in the
772 HsATG4b-LC3 protein complex (PDB ID: 2Z0E) and AtATG4a-AtATG8a 3D
773 structural model.

774 **Supplemental Figure 3.** Conjugation of Chlamydomonas ATG8 processed by ATG4s
775 proteases from Arabidopsis.

776 **Supplemental Figure 4.** Phenotypes of wild-type and *atg4ab* double-mutant seedlings
777 under the basal and induced autophagy conditions.

778 **Supplemental Figure 5.** Alignment of amino acid sequences of ATG4 from various
779 sources.

780 **Supplemental Figure 6.** Lower exposure of the GFP-blot shown in Figure 2.

781

782 **Supplemental Table 1.** Classification of the proteins with persulfidation level reduced
783 after 3 h ABA treatment.

784 **Supplemental Table 2.** Protein list of the elements included in the bin of "proteins"
785 with persulfidation level reduced after 3 h ABA treatment.

786

787 **Supplemental Dataset 1.** Spectral library
788 **Supplemental Dataset 2.** Proteins quantified using SWATH acquisition method in the
789 control sample versus 3 h ABA treatment sample.
790 **Supplemental Dataset 3.** Proteins with different abundance in the control sample
791 compared to that in the 3 h ABA treatment sample at p value <0.05.
792 **Supplemental Dataset 4.** Proteins quantified using SWATH acquisition method in the
793 control sample versus 6 h ABA treatment sample.
794 **Supplemental Dataset 5.** Proteins with different abundance in the control sample
795 compared to that in the 6 h ABA treatment sample at p value <0.05.

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801

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812

813 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

814

815 Á.A., A.M.L-M., M.E.P-P., I.Y., A. J-F. and I.M. performed research and analyzed the
816 data. J.L.C. and L.C.R. designed research and analyze data. C.G. designed the research,
817 analyzed the data, and wrote the article. All authors contributed to the discussion.

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1046 **Figure Legends**

1047

1048 **Figure 1.** Proteomic analysis of protein persulfidation in response to ABA in mesophyll
1049 cells.

1050 (A) Workflow of ABA leaf treatments followed by tag-switch protein labeling with CN-
1051 biotin, protein purification, and quantitative SWATH analysis of eluted proteins.

1052 (B) PCA representation plot of the 18 samples after SWATH analysis. Score for PC1
1053 (70 %) versus PC2 (9.9%), Pareto scaling.

1054 (C) Level of persulfidated ATG4a after ABA treatments. Values represent the mean
1055 peak areas of extracted ion chromatogram of identified ATG4a peptides. *, $p < 0.05$.

1056

1057 **Figure 2.** Effect of sulfide on autophagy induced by ABA treatment.

1058 (A) Immunoblot analysis of GFP-ATG8e fusion protein. One-week-old seedlings
1059 expressing GFP-ATG8e fusion protein were transferred to liquid MS media and were
1060 not treated (control) or treated with 50 μ M ABA for 3 and 6 h and then 200 μ M NaHS
1061 for 1 h. Total protein extracts were prepared and subjected to SDS-PAGE and
1062 immunoblot analysis with anti-GFP antibodies. Anti-tubulin antibodies were used as the
1063 protein-loading control.

1064 (B) Quantification of the free GFP/GFP-ATG8 ratio. For each condition, the levels of
1065 free GFP and GFP-ATG8e fusion protein were quantified in a less exposed blot shown
1066 in Supplemental Figure 6. The value of 100% was assigned to the free GFP/GFP-ATG8
1067 ratio of the control sample. Data are from three independent experiments and evaluated
1068 by two-factor ANOVA. Same letters indicate no significant differences. $P < 0.05$.

1069

1070 **Figure 3.** Persulfidation of Arabidopsis AtATG4a.

1071 (A) Immunoblot analysis of persulfidated AtATG4a. Purified recombinant AtATG4a
1072 was treated in the absence (-) or in the presence of 50 mM DTT (+) for 30 min at 4°C,
1073 dialyzed, and subjected to the tag-switch labeling as described in the Methods. Then,
1074 the proteins were subjected to immunoblot analysis using anti-biotin antibodies. Sypro
1075 Ruby fluorescent staining is shown as the protein loading control.

1076 (B) Analysis of AtATG4a using mass spectrometry. LC-MS/MS analysis of a tryptic
1077 peptide of AtATG4a containing Cys170. The table inside the spectrum contains the
1078 predicted ion types for the modified peptide, and the ions detected in the spectrum are
1079 highlighted in red.

1080 (C) AtATG4a protein sequence identified with 97% coverage. The peptide containing
1081 persulfidated Cys170 is highlighted in yellow and all the Cys residues are red.

1082

1083 **Figure 4.** Arabidopsis ATG4a cleaves Chlamydomonas ATG8.

1084 ATG4 activity of the recombinant AtATG4a was assayed by monitoring the cleavage of
1085 CrATG8 from the unprocessed (CrATG8) to processed (pCrATG8) forms (indicated by
1086 arrowheads) using SDS-PAGE followed by Coomassie Blue staining and quantification
1087 of protein band intensities. The ATG4 activity (relative units) was determined as the
1088 ratio of the band intensity of the processed CrATG8 to the sum of the intensities of the
1089 unprocessed and processed CrATG8. Activity value of 1 corresponds to the maximum.
1090 Processed pCrATG8 (lane 1) and unprocessed CrATG8 (lane 2) were loaded as
1091 controls. Representative images are shown. Data are from three independent
1092 experiments and evaluated by two-factor ANOVA. Same letters indicate no significant
1093 differences. $P < 0.05$.

1094 (A) Effect of incubation time. AtATG4a was incubated with CrATG8 in the absence or
1095 in the presence of 10 mM DTT for the indicated times.

1096 (B) Effect of DTT concentration. AtATG4a was incubated with CrATG8 in the absence
1097 or in the presence of increasing concentrations of DTT for 4 h.

1098 (C) Effect of TCEP concentration. AtATG4a was incubated with CrATG8 in the
1099 absence or in the presence of increasing concentrations of TCEP for 4 h.

1100

1101 **Figure 5.** Effect of NaHS on AtATG4a enzyme activity.

1102 (A) AtATG4a was incubated with 0.5 mM TCEP for 2 h and treated in the absence or in
1103 the presence of indicated concentrations of NaHS for 1 h. Then, CrATG8 was added to
1104 the incubation mixture, and ATG4 activity was monitored after 4 h using Coomassie-
1105 stained gels as described in the Methods. All procedures were performed at 25°C. Lane
1106 1 and 2, unprocessed and processed CrATG8, respectively. Lane 3, AtATG4a incubated
1107 with CrATG8 in the absence of TCEP and of NaHS. Lanes 4-8, TCEP-pretreated
1108 reduced AtATG4a incubated with CrATG8 in the presence of increasing concentrations
1109 of NaHS (from 0 to 1 mM). A representative image is shown.

1110 (B) Quantification of ATG4 activity (relative units) determined as the ratio of the band
1111 intensity of the processed CrATG8 to the sum of the intensities of the unprocessed and
1112 processed CrATG8. A value of 1 corresponds to AtATG4a in the absence of NaHS
1113 (lane 4).

1114 (C) Quantification of the protein band intensity corresponding to the monomeric
1115 AtATG4a form marked by a rectangle in A. A value of 100% corresponds to AtATG4a
1116 in the absence of NaHS (lane 4).

1117 Data are from three independent experiments and evaluated by two-factor ANOVA.

1118 Same letters indicate no significant differences. $P < 0.05$.

1119

1120

1121 **Figure 6.** Effect of polysulfides on AtATG4a enzyme activity.

1122 (A) AtATG4a was incubated with 0.5 mM TCEP for 2 h and subsequently treated in the
1123 absence or in the presence of indicated concentrations of Na_2S_4 for 1 h. Then, CrATG8
1124 was added to the incubation mixture, and ATG4 activity was monitored after 4 h using
1125 Coomassie-stained gels as described in Methods. All procedures were performed at 25
1126 °C. A representative image is shown.

1127 (B) Quantification of ATG4 activity (relative units) determined as the ratio of the band
1128 intensity of the processed CrATG8 to the sum of the intensities of the unprocessed and
1129 processed CrATG8. A value of 1 corresponds to AtATG4a treated in the absence of
1130 Na_2S_4 (lane 1).

1131 (C) Quantification of the protein band intensity corresponding to the monomeric
1132 AtATG4a form marked by a rectangle in A. A value of 100% corresponds to AtATG4a
1133 treated in the absence of Na_2S_4 (lane 1).

1134 (D) Reversibility of the effect. AtATG4a was incubated with 0.25 mM TCEP for 2 h
1135 (lane 1) and treated with 100 μM Na_2S_4 for 1 h (lane 2) and 1 mM TCEP for 1 h (lane
1136 3). ATG4 activity was monitored using Coomassie-stained gels. The experiment was
1137 performed at least three times and a representative image used for the quantification of
1138 the activity is shown.

1139 Data are from three independent experiments and evaluated by two-factor ANOVA.

1140 Same letters indicate no significant differences. $P < 0.05$.

1141

1142

1143 **Figure 7.** Predicted structure of the AtATG4a-AtATG8a complex.

1144 (A) 3D modelling of the AtATG4a-AtATG8a complex based on the structure of the
1145 HsAtg4B-LC3 protein complex (PDB ID: 2Z0E). The AtATG8 protein sequence
1146 (Q8LEM4 in UniProtKB) corresponds to the splice variant 1. Surface representation of
1147 the protein complex and the equivalent residues surrounding the catalytic cavity

1148 Cys170, Trp192, Asp364, and His366 in AtATG4a (red) and Phe116, Gly117, Thr120,
1149 and Ala122 in AtATG8a (blue) are shown in the structural models.

1150 **(B)** Zoomed view of the putative conformation of the active site showing the spheres
1151 corresponding to the position and distance (Å) of catalytic residues Cys170, Trp192,
1152 Asp364, and His366 in AtATG4a.

1153

1154 **Figure 8.** Cleavage and conjugation of Chlamydomonas ATG8 by Arabidopsis
1155 proteins.

1156 **(A)** ATG4 proteolytic activity in wild-type Arabidopsis leaves. Arabidopsis protein
1157 extracts prepared from leaves of wild-type seedlings grown for 11 days on MS medium
1158 were incubated with CrATG8 or site-directed mutant G120A proteins at 25°C for the
1159 indicated times, and ATG4 activity was monitored as the cleavage of the ATG8 forms
1160 to the processed (pCrATG8) forms by immunoblotting analysis with anti-CrATG8.
1161 Processed pCrATG8 (lane 1), unprocessed CrATG8 (lane 2), and site-directed mutant
1162 G120A (lane 6) were loaded as controls.

1163 **(B)** ATG4 proteolytic activity in the Arabidopsis *atg4ab* mutant. Arabidopsis protein
1164 extracts were prepared from the leaves of wild-type and *atg4ab* double mutant seedlings
1165 grown for 7 days on the MS medium and transferred to the same medium (+N) or to a
1166 nitrogen-deficient medium (-N) for additional 4 days. The protein extracts were
1167 incubated with CrATG8 at 25°C, and ATG4 activity was monitored after 0, 0.5, or 2 h
1168 as indicated by immunoblotting analysis with anti-CrATG8.

1169 The arrowheads show the unprocessed CrATG8 and processed pCrATG8 protein bands,
1170 and the asterisks indicate faster-mobility protein bands. Ponceau staining is shown as
1171 the protein loading control of the Arabidopsis extract.

1172

1173 **Figure 9.** Sulfide inhibits the endogenous proteolytic activity of Arabidopsis ATG4.

1174 **(A)** Effect of polysulfides on endogenous enzyme activity of Arabidopsis ATG4.
1175 Arabidopsis protein extracts (Ex) were prepared from the leaves of seedlings grown for
1176 11 days on the MS medium. The extracts were treated in the absence (un-Ex) and in the
1177 presence of 200 μM Na₂S₄ (Na₂S₄-Ex), or 20 mM iodoacetamide (IAM-Ex) for 30 min,
1178 or in the presence of 200 μM Na₂S₄ for 30 min and 1 mM TCEP for 30 min (Na₂S₄-Ex
1179 + TCEP). Then, CrATG8 was added to the incubation mixture, and ATG4 proteolytic
1180 activity was monitored. Lane 1, unprocessed CrATG8.

1181 **(B)** Sulfide reverts the endogenous enzyme activity of Arabidopsis ATG4 under
1182 autophagy-induced conditions. Arabidopsis protein extracts were prepared from the
1183 leaves of seedlings grown for 7 days on the MS medium and transferred to the same
1184 medium (+N) or to a nitrogen-deficient medium (-N) (left panel); or transferred to the
1185 same medium (-mannitol) or to same medium containing 300 mM mannitol (+mannitol)
1186 (right panel) for additional 4 days. The extracts were treated in the absence (un-Ex) or
1187 in the presence of 200 μ M Na₂S₄ for 30 min (Na₂S₄-EX); CrATG8 was added to the
1188 incubation mixture and ATG4 activity was monitored. Lane 1, processed pCrATG8 and
1189 lane 2, unprocessed CrATG8.
1190 The ATG4 activity was monitored at the indicated times by immunoblotting analysis
1191 with anti-CrATG8. All procedures were performed at 25°C. Ponceau staining is shown
1192 as the protein loading control.

1193

1194 **Figure 10.** Graphical model of ABA-triggered induction of autophagy mediated by
1195 posttranslational modification of ATG4. Under basal conditions, intracellular sulfide
1196 maintains high levels of persulfidation of the ATG4 pool, which inhibits the proteolytic
1197 activity of the enzyme for ATG8 C-terminal processing. An increase in the intracellular
1198 level of ABA transiently decreases the level of persulfidation of the ATG4 population
1199 activating the protease activity of the enzyme and the processing of ATG8 that can be
1200 further lipidated to progress autophagy. Yellow circles represent ATG8 protein with or
1201 without the processed C-terminus (represented as X). Blue semicircles represent
1202 persulfidated ATG4 at the thiol group of Cys170 residue. Blue Pacman symbols
1203 represent ATG4 with reduced thiol group of Cys170 residue. The conjugation process
1204 of ATG8 with phosphatidylethanolamine (PE) and autophagosome initiation and
1205 closure are also shown.

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1207

Figure 1. Proteomic analysis of protein persulfidation in response to ABA in mesophyll cells.

(A) Workflow of ABA leaf treatments followed by tag-switch protein labeling with CN-biotin, protein purification, and quantitative SWATH analysis of eluted proteins.

(B) PCA representation plot of the 18 samples after SWATH analysis. Score for PC1 (70 %) versus PC2 (9.9%), Pareto scaling.

(C) Level of persulfidated ATG4a after ABA treatments. Values represent the mean peak areas of extracted ion chromatogram of identified ATG4a peptides. *, $p < 0.05$

Figure 2. Effect of sulfide on autophagy induced by ABA treatment.

(A) Immunoblot analysis of GFP-ATG8e fusion protein. One-week-old seedlings expressing GFP-ATG8e fusion protein were transferred to liquid MS media and were not treated (control) or treated with 50 μ M ABA for 3 and 6 h and then 200 μ M NaHS for 1 h. Total protein extracts were prepared and subjected to SDS-PAGE and immunoblot analysis with anti-GFP antibodies. Anti-tubulin antibodies were used as the protein-loading control.

(B) Quantification of the free GFP/GFP-ATG8 ratio. For each condition, the levels of free GFP and GFP-ATG8e fusion protein were quantified in a less exposed blot shown in Supplemental Figure 6. The value of 100% was assigned to the free GFP/GFP-ATG8 ratio of the control sample. Data are from three independent experiments and evaluated by two-factor ANOVA. Same letters indicate no significant differences. $P < 0.05$.

Figure 3. Persulfidation of Arabidopsis AtATG4a

(A) Immunoblot analysis of persulfidated AtATG4a. Purified recombinant AtATG4a was treated in the absence (–) or in the presence of 50 mM DTT (+) for 30 min at 4°C, dialyzed, and subjected to the tag-switch labeling as described in the Methods. Then, the proteins were subjected to immunoblot analysis using anti-biotin antibodies. Sypro Ruby fluorescent staining is shown as the protein loading control.

(B) Analysis of AtATG4a using mass spectrometry. LC-MS/MS analysis of a tryptic peptide of AtATG4a containing Cys170. The table inside the spectrum contains the predicted ion types for the modified peptide, and the ions detected in the spectrum are highlighted in red.

(C) AtATG4a protein sequence identified with 97% coverage. The peptide containing persulfidated Cys170 is highlighted in yellow and all the Cys residues are red.

Figure 4. Arabidopsis ATG4a cleaves Chlamydomonas ATG8.

ATG4 activity of the recombinant AtATG4a was assayed by monitoring the cleavage of CrATG8 from the unprocessed (CrATG8) to processed (pCrATG8) forms (indicated by arrowheads) using SDS-PAGE followed by Coomassie Blue staining and quantification of protein band intensities. The ATG4 activity (relative units) was determined as the ratio of the band intensity of the processed CrATG8 to the sum of the intensities of the unprocessed and processed CrATG8. Activity value of 1 corresponds to the maximum. Processed pCrATG8 (lane 1) and unprocessed CrATG8 (lane 2) were loaded as controls. Representative images are shown. Data are from three independent experiments and evaluated by two-factor ANOVA. Same letters indicate no significant differences. $P < 0.05$.

(A) Effect of incubation time. AtATG4a was incubated with CrATG8 in the absence or in the presence of 10 mM DTT for the indicated times.

(B) Effect of DTT concentration. AtATG4a was incubated with CrATG8 in the absence or in the presence of increasing concentrations of DTT for 4 h.

(C) Effect of TCEP concentration. AtATG4a was incubated with CrATG8 in the absence or in the presence of increasing concentrations of TCEP for 4 h.

Figure 5. Effect of NaHS on AtATG4a enzyme activity.

(A) AtATG4a was incubated with 0.5 mM TCEP for 2 h and treated in the absence or the presence of indicated concentrations of NaHS for 1 h. Then, CrATG8 was added to the incubation mixture, and ATG4 activity was monitored after 4 h using Coomassie-stained gels as described in the Methods. All procedures were performed at 25°C. Lane 1 and 2, unprocessed and processed CrATG8, respectively. Lane 3, AtATG4a incubated with CrATG8 in the absence of TCEP and of NaHS. Lanes 4-8, TCEP-pretreated reduced AtATG4a incubated with CrATG8 in the presence of increasing concentrations of NaHS (from 0 to 1 mM). A representative image is shown.

(B) Quantification of ATG4 activity (relative units) determined as the ratio of the band intensity of the processed CrATG8 to the sum of the intensities of the unprocessed and processed CrATG8. A value of 1 corresponds to AtATG4a in the absence of NaHS (lane 4).

(C) Quantification of the protein band intensity corresponding to the monomeric AtATG4a form marked by a rectangle in A. A value of 100% corresponds to AtATG4a in the absence of NaHS (lane 4).

Data are from three independent experiments and evaluated by two-factor ANOVA. Same letters indicate no significant differences. $P < 0.05$

Figure 6. Effect of polysulfides on AtATG4a enzyme activity.

(A) AtATG4a was incubated with 0.5 mM TCEP for 2 h and subsequently treated in the absence or in the presence of indicated concentrations of Na_2S_4 for 1 h. Then, CrATG8 was added to the incubation mixture, and ATG4 activity was monitored after 4 h using Coomassie-stained gels as described in Methods. All procedures were performed at 25°C. A representative image is shown.

(B) Quantification of ATG4 activity (relative units) determined as the ratio of the band intensity of the processed CrATG8 to the sum of the intensities of the unprocessed and processed CrATG8. A value of 1 corresponds to AtATG4a treated in the absence of Na_2S_4 (lane 1).

(C) Quantification of the protein band intensity corresponding to the monomeric AtATG4a form marked by a rectangle in A. A value of 100% corresponds to AtATG4a treated in the absence of Na_2S_4 (lane 1).

(D) Reversibility of the effect. AtATG4a was first incubated with 0.25 mM TCEP for 2 h (lane 1) and treated with 100 μM Na_2S_4 for 1 h (lane 2) and 1 mM TCEP for 1 h (lane 3). ATG4 activity was monitored using Coomassie-stained gels. The experiment was performed at least three times and a representative image used for the quantification of the activity is shown.

Data are from three independent experiments and evaluated by two-factor ANOVA. Same letters indicate no significant differences. $P < 0.05$

Figure 7. Predicted structure of the AtATG4a-AtATG8a complex.

(A) 3D modelling of the AtATG4a-AtATG8a complex based on the structure of the HsAtg4B-LC3 protein complex (PDB ID: 2Z0E). The AtATG8 protein sequence (Q8LEM4 in UniProtKB) corresponds to the splice variant 1. Surface representation of the protein complex and the equivalent residues surrounding the catalytic cavity Cys170, Trp192, Asp364, and His366 in AtATG4a (red) and Phe116, Gly117, Thr120, and Ala122 in AtATG8a (blue) are shown in the structural models.

(B) Zoomed view of the putative conformation of the active site showing the spheres corresponding to the position and distance (Å) of catalytic residues Cys170, Trp192, Asp364, and His366 in AtATG4a.

Figure 8. Cleavage and conjugation of Chlamydomonas ATG8 by Arabidopsis proteins.

(A) ATG4 proteolytic activity in wild-type Arabidopsis leaves. Arabidopsis protein extracts prepared from leaves of wild-type seedlings grown for 11 days on MS medium were incubated with CrATG8 or site-directed mutant G120A proteins at 25°C for the indicated times, and ATG4 activity was monitored as the cleavage of the ATG8 forms to the processed (pCrATG8) forms by immunoblotting analysis with anti-CrATG8. Processed pCrATG8 (lane 1), unprocessed CrATG8 (lane 2), and site-directed mutant G120A (lane 6) were loaded as controls.

(B) ATG4 proteolytic activity in the Arabidopsis *atg4ab* mutant. Arabidopsis protein extracts were prepared from the leaves of wild-type and *atg4ab* double mutant seedlings grown for 7 days on the MS medium and transferred to the same medium (+N) or to a nitrogen-deficient medium (-N) for additional 4 days. The protein extracts were incubated with CrATG8 at 25°C, and ATG4 activity was monitored after 0, 0.5, or 2 h, as indicated by immunoblotting analysis with anti-CrATG8.

The arrowheads show the unprocessed CrATG8 and processed pCrATG8 protein bands, and the asterisks indicate faster-mobility protein bands. Ponceau staining is shown as the protein loading control of the Arabidopsis extract.

Figure 9. Sulfide inhibits the endogenous proteolytic activity of Arabidopsis ATG4.

(A) Effect of polysulfides on endogenous enzyme activity of Arabidopsis ATG4. Arabidopsis protein extracts (Ex) were prepared from the leaves of seedlings grown for 11 days on the MS medium. The extracts were treated in the absence (un-Ex) and in the presence of 200 μM Na_2S_4 ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ex}$), or 20 mM iodoacetamide (IAM-Ex) for 30 min, or in the presence of 200 μM Na_2S_4 for 30 min and 1 mM TCEP for 30 min ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ex} + \text{TCEP}$). Then, CrATG8 was added to the incubation mixture, and ATG4 proteolytic activity was monitored. Lane 1, unprocessed CrATG8.

(B) Sulfide reverts the endogenous enzyme activity of Arabidopsis ATG4 under autophagy-induced conditions. Arabidopsis protein extracts were prepared from the leaves of seedlings grown for 7 days on the MS medium and transferred to the same medium (+N) or to a nitrogen-deficient medium (-N) (left panel); or transferred to the same medium (-mannitol) or to same medium containing 300 mM mannitol (+mannitol) (right panel) for additional 4 days. The extracts were treated in the absence (un-Ex) or in the presence of 200 μM Na_2S_4 for 30 min ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ex}$); CrATG8 was added to the incubation mixture and ATG4 activity monitored. Lane 1, processed pCrATG8 and lane 2, unprocessed CrATG8.

The ATG4 activity was monitored at the indicated times by immunoblotting analysis with anti-CrATG8. All procedures were performed at 25°C. Ponceau staining is shown as the protein loading control.

Figure 10. Graphical model of ABA-triggered autophagy induction through ATG4 posttranslational modification. Under basal conditions intracellular sulfide maintains high levels of persulfidation of the ATG4 pool which inhibits the proteolytic activity of the enzyme for ATG8 C-terminal processing. Increase in the intracellular level of ABA transiently decreases the level of persulfidation of the ATG4 population, activating the protease activity of the enzyme and the processing of ATG8 that can be further lipidated for the progression of autophagy. Yellow circles represent ATG8 protein with or without the C-terminal processed end (represented as X). Blue semicircles represent persulfidated ATG4 protein at the thiol ^{170}Cys residue. Blue Pacman symbols represent ATG4 protein with reduced thiol ^{170}Cys residue. The conjugation process of ATG8 with phosphatidylethanolamine (PE), autophagosome initiation and closure are also shown.

IN A NUTSHELL

Background: Hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) is a poisonous substance hazardous to life and the environment, but it is also present in biological tissues. Intense investigation showed that H_2S functions as an important regulator of essential processes in animals and plants. For example, our previous research on the plant *Arabidopsis* demonstrated that H_2S regulates autophagy. In autophagy (which is conserved in plants and animals), cell contents are digested for recycling. The materials to be digested are sequestered in a double membrane-bound structures called autophagosomes and the proteins involved in the main molecular machinery are referred to as autophagy-related (ATG). Autophagy is involved in plant development, immune responses, and adaptation to adverse environmental conditions.

Question: We wanted to know the mechanism of action by which H_2S regulates autophagy. Previous findings showed that H_2S is not a reductant in autophagy. We want to determine if the mechanism is persulfidation, a posttranslational protein modification of the thiol group of cysteines to form a persulfide group, and to identify the target ATG proteins.

Findings: Using proteomic analysis of *Arabidopsis* leaves treated with the hormone abscisic acid (ABA), we found that persulfidation of the cysteine protease ATG4 controls autophagy. When the persulfidation level of ATG4 is reduced after a short ABA treatment the autophagy progresses. This ATG4 protease undergoes specific persulfidation of the Cys170 residue that is a part of the catalytic site. ATG4 catalyzes the processing of newly synthesized ATG8, which is essential for the synthesis of autophagosomes. This activity was measured in a heterologous assay using *Chlamydomonas* ATG8 as substrate and we demonstrated that H_2S significantly and reversibly inactivates the proteolytic activity of ATG4. Under autophagy-inducing conditions such as nitrogen starvation and osmotic stress, we detected a significant increase in the overall ATG4 proteolytic activity that can be inhibited by sulfide.

Next steps: Our study demonstrated that negative regulation of autophagy by H_2S is mediated by persulfidation of ATG4. Probably this is not the only protein and additional targets remain to be identified. We will also investigate the role of H_2S in the regulation of selective autophagy and the interplay between H_2S and other regulators.

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